

Plant Care MANUAL

Developing capacity for Indigenous Community Agroforestry
in the Amadiba area of Eastern Mpondoland

To secure the plant and remove any air pockets around the roots, hold the main stem, and use your hands or feet to press down gently on the soil around the plant.

To measure root collar circumference, circle the measuring tape around the portion of the stem that emerges from the ground (root collar). To measure plant height, measure from the root collar to the uppermost (apex) leaf shoot.

METADATA

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Fox, F.W., & Norwood Young, M.E. (1982). Food from the Veld: edible plants of South Africa. Delta Books, Johannesburg. ISBN 0908387326.

PlantZAfrica <http://pza.sanbi.org/>

Useful Tropical Plants <http://tropical.theferns.info/>

World Agroforestry Centre <https://apps.worldagroforestry.org/treedb/>

The project is a collaboration between the Institute of Natural Resources (INR), Sustaining the Wild Coast (SWC), and Siyasisiza Trust (ST) working together with residents of the Amadiba Coastal Villages in Eastern Mpondoland. Within this collaboration, INR brings the scientific and technical aspects of indigenous agroforestry species, the local SWC team provides leadership within Amadiba and ST brings technical expertise in the locally established agroecology infrastructure.

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INTRODUCTION

The Amadiba area in the Eastern Cape, South Africa is a biodiversity hotspot, and one of the few extant indigenous communities that practice traditional farming. This area faces threat from invasive alien encroachment, coastal erosion, land degradation and abandonment, and a drain on biocultural heritage due to youth out-migration.

The project is engaging the residents of the six villages constituting the Amadiba area in selecting, planting, propagating, and utilizing locally appropriate indigenous tree species to enhance their livelihoods. These trees will be effective in contributing to food security and the household economy in the form of non-timber forest products (fibre, fodder, medicine, wood). The project has planted 2700 plants belonging to 32 species over an area of 125 hectares in the six communities, with the aim of promoting climate resilient agroforestry. The project has undertaken participatory mapping to identify, prioritise, design, and plant in selected places in their communities to provide agroforestry functions such as food provisioning, live fencing, windbreaks, soil stabilisation, and water sequestration.

The communities will be trained to monitor, propagate, and sustainably use the tree species for their own use, and will also plan for potential market-based enterprises based on propagation and plant-derived products in future. The project will build capacity in members of the community including women and youth in agroforestry design, plant propagation, sustainable use, and enterprise opportunities. This set of manuals documents the procedures used to plant the species, care for them, and monitor their growth over a 6 month period. It also presents general principles for sustainable use of the species, and techniques for their propagation.

PLANTING PROTOCOL

A. Digging

1. Measure and mark the planting sites, noting the width and depth of the holes, and spacing between them, as displayed in the reference sheet. Leave at least one metre between plants expected to grow into hedges, and more (as recommended in reference sheet) for larger plants. We are leaving five metres between large, shade-giving trees, three metres between wind-breaking and woody trees, and two metres where planting to prevent erosion by water or wind.
2. Open up the soil by dropping the shovel and carving out the topsoil. Heap the topsoil together in one place or container for later use. The topsoil is about 10 to 20cm of dark, moist soil, followed by lighter coloured, tighter textured soil that can be heaped separately. If the soil beneath the topsoil is very rocky, consider relocating the hole.
3. Holes usually have equal width, depth, and height. Deepen and widen the hole to required depth, making sure that the hole stays equally wide throughout: the hole should be a square or cylinder, not a U or V shaped pit.

4. Fill the completed hole with water and allow all the water to sink into the ground. We skipped this step because there was heavy rain in the preceding days, and the soil was already quite wet.

B. Setting

5. Gently free the plant from its container by tapping or squeezing; the aim is to keep maximum soil intact on the roots. If applying soil treatments like compost or manure, spread a thin layer of the material at the bottom of the hole; this is optional.
6. Lower the plant into the wet hole, and ensure that there is enough space for all the roots, in depth and width. The roots should not be squeezed, bent, or exposed. Adjust the hole size if needed, to fully and freely accommodate the roots. They should sit an inch below the ground. The leaves and branches should all be above the ground.
7. Ensuring that the roots sit an inch below the ground and the leaves are above the ground, fill the hole back first with the topsoil. If needed, add compost, more soil, or potting mixture until the hole is full.

C. Securing

8. Hold the main stem of the plant (and any low leaves), and use the hands or feet to press down gently on the soil around the plant stem; the aim is to remove excess air pockets to prevent root drying.
9. Add more soil to fill the hole if required, and ensure that the stem sits an inch below ground level. Create a ring of soil around the plant to act as a trench to retain water.
10. Water the plant to fill the trench and let it sink in. Apply light mulch inside and or along the trench if necessary.

Figure 1: When planting, allow appropriate space between any two plants for live fences (1m), soil protection (2m), windbreaks (3m) and shade (5m); dig holes as deep and wide as the plant roots; place the roots to have enough space without being compressed, raised or exposed.

PLANT CARE

Congratulations on having planted hundreds of indigenous trees and shrubs in your community! We hope that they will all survive and provide the functions we planned for. Some basic care in the first year will go a long way in ensuring that the plants become self-sufficient. During the first summer, that is between December 2024 and April 2025, the trees will require the most attention. We recommend watering the plants weekly, and at the same time checking them for signs of health.

A. Watering

Water the plant until the bowl-like depression surrounding it is full. This indicates that the soil around the roots is soaked with water. If there is no depression, try to create one by moving the soil around the root collar to form a slightly raised ring around the plant.

When watering, check the soil. If it is cracked or caked, the soil is too dry, and needs more water. If it is soggy or mouldy, it is too wet, and needs to dry a little. Adjust the amount of water provided depending on the condition. After watering, cover the soil with mulch to reduce water evaporation and erosion.

B. Roots

Check that the roots of the plant are firm and underground. If any roots are exposed or burrowed into, add soil and compact it using the balls of the hands or feet. Ensure that none of the leaves or branches of the soil are buried, as this may affect the plant's health.

If the plant is small and still close to the ground, ensure that the ring around the plant is free from other live grasses and herbs. This will enable it to get light, and absorb sufficient water and nutrients from the soil, without competition. If the plant is above waist height, this should not be a problem.

C. Stem and leaves

If a plant sheds most of its leaves and only the stem remains, it may be defending itself against extreme conditions. Do not assume that it is dead. Check the stem for flexibility and greenness. If the stem doesn't break when bent, scratch the bark with a fingernail; if the stem is still green, the plant is alive, and will likely sprout more leaves when conditions improve. Continue caring for it like a live plant.

Check the stem and the leaves for any signs of damage. If these parts are shrivelled, the plant may need more water and shade. If these parts have different coloured spots, they may be suffering from a root or leaf disease. If they have holes or torn edges, they may be facing attack from insects. Note down these signs and inform the Farmer Forum.

Adjust watering if the plant roots, stem, or leaves are wilting. Pluck and dispose leaves that are spotted or damaged, to discourage spread of the disease or the pest. Check the plant for caterpillars, grasshoppers, fungus, etc, and remove them by hand.

D. Interventions

If plants consistently show signs of ill-health (wilting, spotting, damage) for three weeks, they may need interventions. If the plants are wilting from overexposure to sun or wind, consider installing shade net around them. If the plants are suffering from disease or pests, they may need to be transplanted to a different place in the autumn. If the signs of disease spread to other plants over the course of a week, the affected plants should be removed from the site immediately.

In case of extreme weather such as a very hot day or heavy rain, check on the plants as soon as possible when conditions are normal again. Apply the steps above to ensure that the plants are in good health.

Next Steps for 2025

The project team will return in February 2025 to follow up on the plants and discuss with the community what we are learning. Together, we will undertake the following activities:

1. Counting plants and noting their health

When planting in November 2024, we counted how many plants were placed at each of the sites. To understand if we made the correct choice of plants, we will count how many of the plants survived, how many did not, and what the health condition of each plant is. We will note if any of the plants are suffering from disease or pests as noted above.

2. Measuring the health and root collar diameter of plants marked for long-term observation

In November 2024, we marked some plants with yellow tape, and measured their height and root collar diameter. We will take these measurements for the same plants again in February 2024. This will help us to understand the rate at which the plants are growing, so that we can estimate at what time the plants may mature and bear fruit.

3. Discussing the things we have learned and planned

Together, we will discuss the weather and plant conditions we have observed in the three months. We will decide how to overcome any problems, and plan how to care for the plants. We will make note of all our learnings and plans.

LONG-TERM OBSERVATION

We have planted 2747 plants at 22 sites in November 2024 (Table 1). It would be ideal to keep track of how many of these plants survive, and how they grow, every season. The project team will visit in February and May 2024 to track these plants and show the community how to do the same for the future.

The project team has marked about 124 plants at eight sites for long-term observation. These plants have yellow tape tied around them, with their scientific name written on the tape. These plants have been and will be measured for their root collar diameter (rcd) and total height. These measurements can provide useful information about the ongoing growth and health of young plants. The intended outcome of these measurements is to establish the growth rate of the species, which can indicate the health of the species, and also allow for comparisons with known growth rates of cultivated species.

Table 1: List of sites and number of plants planted through the project at each of the six communities in Amadiba

Site	Planted (n)	Observation plants (n)	Area (ha)	Community	Community Plant Total (n)
Mdatya School	102	20 (Approx)	2.3	Mdatya	346
Sijadu School	155	20 (Approx)	7.9		
Mdatya Erosion	89	0	0.6		
Bhekela School	371	0	0.9	Bhekela	371
Mtolani Community Garden	75	16	0.2	Mtolani	361
Mtolani Nursery	41	4	0.02		
Mnyameni Homestay	49	3	0.4		
Dukisa Homestead	34	0	0.1		
Komkhulu Community Centre	162	0	na	Mphindweni	443
Kwanyana Lodge	121	0	1.0		
Kwanyana Community Garden and Nursery	104	0	1.3		
Mthwa Homestead	40	0	0.2		
Xolobeni School	50	16	3.2		
Trayi Homestead	128	0	0.06	Nyavini	680
Sikhombe Dunes	283	0	2.5		
Dumasi Hall	183	0	0.3		
Dumasi Creche	112	18	0.08		
Six Community Gardens	102	0	0.03	Gobodweni	546
Masizame Creche	84	0	0.3		
Baleni School	166	27	3.7		
Amadiba Community Network Centre	229	0	0.3		
Mzwandile Nursery	67	0	0.1		
Total	2747	124 (Approx)	25.5		2747

The measurement of small plants can easily be done using measuring tape. The root collar is the portion of the stem that emerges from the ground. This part is circled with tape and measured for the circumference. The root collar diameter is calculated by dividing the measured circumference by 3.14. The height of the plant is the measurement from the root collar to the uppermost (or apex) leaf shoot. For plants that have multiple stems, the broadest stem is measured for rcd, and the tallest shoot is measured for height. Measurements for the planted species are in Table A at the end of this booklet.

For plants that are over two metres tall, the approximate height can be measured using a ruler, a tape, and two people. Try to take this measurement by standing at the same level as the tree, that is, not on a slope that places you much above or below the root collar of the tree. Hold one end of the ruler upright in your hand, perpendicular to the ground. Keeping the ruler perpendicular, stretch your arm fully out ahead, parallel to the ground. Walk away from the tree until the ruler and the tree appear to be the same height, and mark this point on the ground. Use a tape to measure the distance between where you stand (the ruler and the tree

are the same height), and the root collar of the plant you are measuring. This distance is nearly equal to the height of the tree. The project team will endeavour to bring a clinometer for more accurate measurements, and show the communities how to use it to calculate tree height.

Once we have at least three sets of measurements, that is, by June 2025, we can start to calculate growth rates for each of the species. This will help us to estimate the number of years until the tree attains maturity and starts fruiting. For example:

- We know that *Harpephyllum caffrum*, the umgwenye, matures at about 7m height.
- It has grown from 37cm at planting, to 81cm in February, to 123cm in May.
- Therefore, it has grown 44cm in the summer, 42cm in the autumn, at the rate of 43cm a quarter.
- This means that the plant is growing 14.3cm per month, and about 171.6cm per year.
- At this rate, the plant will reach a height of 7m and therefore maturity, in about 4 years time.

SUSTAINABLE USE

Once a plant has matured, it will start bearing fruits during certain times of the year. Its growth rate, which has been fast during its younger years, will slow down. The plant may gain in width, through a thickening stem, and roots and branches that spread outward more than upward. Mature plants can offer many useful parts, in the form of fruits, flowers, leaves, seeds, and wood. What can be taken from the plant, and when (seasons) and how (techniques), can be found in the catalogue of species that the project team will bring along in February 2025.

Some general principles to follow when harvesting any products from plants:

1. Do not damage the plant's roots or stems, as these are key to its survival. If taking wood, pick the smaller, farther branches rather than the bigger branches closer to the trunk. If taking bark or roots, carefully and sparingly take small patches from the surface, removing no more than one quarter of the girth of the branch, stem, or root. This will allow the plant to recover from the injury being inflicted.
2. Take only what you need, or about half of the plant's fruits, flowers, and leaves. Remember that the plant needs these parts to make its food to survive, and seeds to procreate. Other animals, birds, and insects also visit the plant for food. Pluck these parts carefully and selectively, to avoid damaging the branches.
3. Try to harvest by hand, selecting ripe fruits, tender leaves, and other desired parts. If using a blade to take wood, bark, or root, use swift and precise cuts to minimise injury to the plant. If fruits or leaves are out of reach, use a ladder or a fruit picker to reach them. Some plants shed ripe fruit readily during fruiting season - try to catch these in a cloth or net raised above the ground to reduce fruit damage by impact, insects, and animals.

PLANT PROPAGATION

Most of the plants we know reproduce themselves by bearing seeds. These seeds are often borne inside a fruit or a pod. A plant needs to bear flowers, which exchange pollen between male and female parts, and then form the fruit or pod. Most plant flowers have male and female parts, so that one plant can produce flowers, fruits, and seeds on its own. Bees, insects, and some nectar-feeding birds like sunbirds help move pollen from male parts to female parts of flowers. However, some plants have separate male and female flowers, and sometimes, only one type of flower is borne by a single plant. A male plant of this type will need bees, insects and birds to transport its pollen to a female plant that is flowering, and vice versa. Only when a female plant is thus fertilised will the plant be able to produce fruits and seeds. In another type of plants, flowering, fruiting, and seeding happens rarely, and the plants reproduce more often by sending out suckers. Suckers are young branches that have the capacity to rapidly grow roots, and break off from the parent plant, to form a new plant which is identical to the parent.

Let us look at the different ways in which we can enable our plants to reproduce. We have planted up to 32 different species of plants across the Amadiba region (Table 2). Of these, 20 plant species will easily grow from

seed. Eight of the 32 species are dioecious, meaning that all the flowers on one plant are either male or female. Therefore, they need at least two or more plants within a close distance to be able to produce fruits. We hope that at least one of the plants is different from the others. If fruits do not set in a season, then another new plant not related to the non-fruiting plants (i.e. grown from a seed) is needed. Four of the 32 species are easier to propagate from cuttings than from seed. Plants grown from cuttings tend to be identical to their parents, so only make cuttings from healthy, robust, and resilient plants.

1. Propagating from seed

1.1. Fresh seeds

The best way to propagate a plant from its seed is to use a ripe fruit. Clean the flesh from the ripened fruit, and sow the seed in one to two inches of soil. Position the seed in such a way that it receives sunlight, but is protected from strong rain or wind. Seeds of ilala and umphafa (*Hyphaene coriacea* and *Ziziphus mucronata*) need to be cracked open from a nut. Seeds of umthongwane, injomi, umkuhlu, and umphafa (*Englerophytum natalense*, *Syzygium cordatum*, *Trichilia emetica*, *Ziziphus mucronata*) need to be fresh when planting, i.e., they cannot be stored from a previous season. Consider the plant's natural habitat and current weather conditions when deciding how much and how frequently to water the seed after sowing. Plants requiring light to moderate watering can be moistened once a week, whereas those requiring well-drained soil can be checked and adjusted for soil moisture daily. Table 2 provides guidelines for watering intensity and germination times for some plants. Upon germination, seedlings should be sheltered from extreme weather until they reach a height of 50cm. After this stage, they can be planted in exposed places as required.

1.2. Treated seeds

Some fresh seeds (*Diospyros whyteana*, *Mimusops zeyheri*) need scarification, also known as scratching, to activate them. Rub the seed coat lightly with a stone, nail file, or knife edge, to scarify the seed. Try to lightly scarify the seed all over, going no deeper than the seed coat. Then sow the seed as usual. Some fresh seeds like those of umqokolo, umpayi, and umthumbu (*Dovyalis caffra*, *Ficus natalensis* and *Ficus sur*) need to be dried in the shade for 24 hours before sowing into soil. Some fresh seeds with hard coverings need soaking overnight in water to activate them. Seeds of umdubu, umgwenya, umsimbeeti, and umkuhlu (*Combretum erythrophyllum*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Millettia grandis*, and *Trichilia emetica*) need soaking overnight in regular water. Seeds of umgadankawu, amathungula, umbhongisa, and umphafa (*Albizia adianthifolia*, *Carissa spp*, *Diospyros lycoides*, and *Ziziphus mucronata*) need to be soaked in warm water overnight. Use warm, but not boiling water for these seeds. Soaked seeds that are swollen and softened are ready to be sown into soil.

1.3. Stored seeds

Seeds of some plants can be stored for a season, or up to a year. Seeds of umgadankawu, amathungula, umbinza, umgwenya, ilala, amavilo and red milkwood (*Albizia adianthifolia*, *Carissa spp*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Hyphaene coriacea*, *Vangueria infausta*, and *Mimusops zeyheri*) can be stored. When storing seeds, clean any coverings off them, dry them

Table 2: Propagation methods for species planted in the six communities of Amadiba

Species	Local name	Propagation Best Option	Option 2	Option 3	Germination	Water
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu, umhlandlothi	Fresh seeds soaked in hot water overnight	Seeds stored up to 3 months soaked in hot water overnight			Moderate amount
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	Fresh seed			5 - 9 days	Light
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini	Fresh seed			2 - 3 months	Moderate amount
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	Fresh or stored seeds (up to 12 months) soaked in hot water overnight	Cuttings	Air layering	2 months	Light; drought hardy
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	Fresh or stored seeds (up to 12 months) soaked in hot water overnight	Cuttings	Air layering	7 - 14 days	
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	Fresh or stored seeds (up to 12 months) soaked in hot water overnight	Cuttings	Air layering		Moderate
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	Fresh seed soaked overnight			7 - 14 days	
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		Seeds			14	Light
<i>Diospyros lycioides</i>	umbhongisa	Seeds soaked in hot water overnight				
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	Seed which must be scratched/sacrificed before sowing			4 - 8 weeks	Moderate
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	umqokolo	Seeds, cleaned and shade dried	Cuttings		18 - 20 days	
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	Fresh seed			2 - 3 weeks	Well watered
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	Truncheons	Cuttings	Seeds		Moderate
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umpayi, amakhiwane	Cuttings	Seeds			Well watered
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbu, amakhiwane	Air layering	Cuttings	Seeds	15 - 20 days	Well watered
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	Seed	Grafting		6 months	
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	Seed				Well watered
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	Seed	Cuttings	Truncheons	6 weeks	Moderate
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenya	Seeds soaked overnight	Cuttings	Truncheons	7 - 11 days	Well watered
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		Seed	Cuttings			Well watered
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	Cuttings	Seeds		8 weeks	Well watered
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	Suckers	Cracked seeds		14 - 180 days	Well watered
<i>Milletia grandis</i>	umsimbeeti	Fresh seed soaked overnight				Well watered
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>		Fresh seed	Stored seed scarified before sowing		2 weeks	Well watered
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	Suckers	Seeds		2 - 3 months	Well watered
<i>Portulacaria afra</i>	igqwanitsha	Cuttings			4 - 6 weeks	Light
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga, ikhamanga	Suckers	Seeds			Well watered
<i>Syzigium cordatum</i>	injomi, umdoni	Fresh seed			25 days	Well watered
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	Cuttings	Fresh seeds			Moderate amount
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	Fresh seed soaked overnight	Suckers	Air layering	10 - 20 days	Moderate amount
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	Suckers	Seeds	Cuttings		
<i>Ziziphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	Fresh seed soaked in hot water overnight			1 - 2 weeks	Moderate

in the shade for at least 24 hours, and store them in a cool, dry, shaded place. Exposure to sunlight, moisture, or insects can destroy stored seeds, so be careful to store seeds in shaded, dry, clean places. When using stored seed for planting, ensure that the seed has not been visited by insects. The stored seeds of red milkwood (*Mimusops zeyheri*) need to be scarified before planting. Soak any stored seed in warm water overnight to activate it. When soaking seeds, activate them with warm, but not boiling water. Then sow the seed as usual.

2. Propagating from cuttings

2.1. Suckers

Some plants naturally produce suckers, which are extensions of the plant that sprout from underground. The roots of the plant send out a new shoot that looks and behaves like a new plant next to the established plant. This sucker can be carefully detached from the older plant, and planted in a desired location. To cut a sucker from an established plant, loosen the soil around the roots of the sucker, and make a clean cut from the parent plant. Try not to disturb the parent plant as far as possible. When transplanting the sucker, ensure all the roots are secured as described in the planting protocol. The ilala, isundu, skamanga, umkuhlu, and amavilo (*Hyphaene coraicea*, *Phoenix reclinata*, *Strelitzia nicolai*, *Trichilia emetica*, and *Vangueria infasuta*) produce suckers. Suckers produce plants identical to the parent, and ilala and isundu are dioecious. This means that a male palm will produce a male sucker, and therefore, will require the presence of a different female palm if it had to produce fruit. Consider this when planting palms if you would like them to fruit.

2.2. Cuttings

Cuttings are sections of plant stems taken from a mature plant and induced to produce roots and an independent plant. Cuttings are taken from a well-established stem, usually by removing a flexible lateral branch from the base. The branch can be 5 to 15cm long, and must include part of the main stem (the heel) and at least one bud, preferably at its tip (the apex shoot). This branch should be removed using a single cut at 45 degrees to the main stem, with minimum damage to the branch or the stem. Any leaves and buds near the heel of this cutting are removed, and the heel is dipped in a rooting medium if this is available. The heel of the cutting is planted in semi-shade, and cared for as described in the seed propagation section. The heel usually develops roots in one month, after which the cutting is an independent plant that can survive exposure. During this time, observe the plant for any signs of disease described in the plant care section. The amathungula, umqokolo, umsinsi, umpayi or amakhiwane, umthumbu, amabimbi, umbinza, umgwenya, orange bird-berry, uthongothi, spekboom or igqwanitsha, iboza, and amavilo (*Carissa* spp., *Dovyalis caffra*, *Erythrina lysistemom*, *Ficus natalensis*, *Ficus sur*, *Garcinia livingstonei*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Hoslundia opposita*, *Hyperacanthus amoenus*, *Portulacaria afra*, *Tetradenia riparia*, and *Vangueria infausta*) can be propagated by cuttings. Note that amathungula, umqokolo, amabimbi, and umgwenya are dioecious, and therefore, their cuttings will produce plants of the same gender as their parent. Consider this when planting these trees if you would like them to fruit.

2.3. Truncheons

Truncheons are entire branches of a plant taken from a mature plant, and induced to produce an independent plant identical to the parent plant. Truncheons are between one and two metres long, and have a firm central stem. Similar to cuttings, remove the truncheon from the main stem with a single, clean 45 degree cut. Take the truncheon into a shaded place and allow it to dry for 24 hours, not longer. Remove any leaves and buds at the bottom 50cm section of the heel, and apply rooting hormones to this section if these are available. Plant the truncheon by burying the heel firmly into the ground, ensuring that the truncheon is upright and supported if needed. Care for the truncheons as described in the plant care section. Truncheons are best taken in the spring or autumn. The umsinsi, umbinza, umgwenya, and umkuhlu (*Erythrina lysistemom*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, and *Trichilia emetica*) can be propagated by truncheons. Truncheons produce plants identical to the parent. Therefore, truncheons of umgwenya, which are dioecious, will be the same gender – either male or female – as their parent. Consider this when planting umgwenya if you would like them to fruit.

2.4. Air layering

Air layering is the process of inducing a branch of a plant to produce roots and form an independent plant, while still attached to the parent plant. To air layer a plant, select a straight, firm, well-established stem that can be broken off later without damaging the plant. Select a section of the stem at least 50cm away from the tip of this stem, where the roots will be induced to grow. In this section, remove any leaves, and remove the bark of the stem using a blade. The bark should be removed all around the stem, and for at least 5cm, exposing the yellow-green core inside. Apply rooting hormones to the exposed section if these are available. Wrap a plastic bag snugly around the bottom of this section, using an elastic band, cable tie, or thread. Fill the plastic bag with moist sphagnum moss, or a moist mix of fibre and potting soil, to cover the exposed section fully. Wrap the filled bag around the section tightly, and close the bag at the top of the section.

The section will require anywhere between one month and one year to sprout roots inside the bag. During this time, keep the section moist, and check weekly for roots, and observe the plant for signs of disease described in the plant care section. Once the roots grow to 5cm, the plant is ready to be detached from the parent plant and planted in the ground. Air layering is best done in the spring or autumn. The amathungula, umthumbu or amakhiwane, and umkuhlu (*Carissa* spp., *Ficus sur*, and *Trichilia emetica*) can be air layered. Air layering produces plants that are the same as their parents. Consider this when air layering amathungula, which is dioecious, and will therefore be either male or female, just like its parent plant.

3. General considerations

We have selected plants that will do well and already grow naturally in the Amadiba region. However, when planting outside of the area, people need to be aware of the conditions under which these plants will thrive. Important considerations are the range of temperatures and rainfall that a plant can survive in, the amount of light and type of soil the plant prefers, and the altitude above sea level, and any atmospheric conditions that the plant is sensitive to. More information for each species can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Growing conditions for the species planted at the six Amadiba communities

Species	Local name	Occurrence	Temperature	Rainfall	Light	Soil	Sensitivity	Growth rate
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu, umhlandlothi	Coastal and low-altitude forest, forest margins, open forest and ravines, 250 - 450m	22 - 28°C but can tolerate 15 - 34°C	1,500 - 2,500mm but tolerates 900 - 4,000mm	Full sun	Sandy loam, pH 4 - 7	Frost	2m per year
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	Woodland, bushveld, rocky areas, along rivers, streams, on old termite mounds, south- and east-facing slopes of mountains	12 - 36°C	0 - 35mm per week	Full sun	Sandy loam, pH 6.5	Frost	Moderate
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini	Variety of habitats from coastal and montane forest, dune forest and forest margins, to bushveld and rocky grasslands, up to 1,700m	Temperate		Full sun, semi-shade	Sandy, clay, loam	Cannot survive arid conditions	Rapid growth after germination
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	Woodland, in woodland fringes, and on maritime dunes, up to 1600m	Tropical and sub-tropical (avg of 25°C)		Full sun or light shade	Sandy loam, pH 6.5	Half frost-hardy	300mm per year, matures at 2 - 3 years
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	Deciduous forest and coastal thickets, up to 2000m	19 - 30°C	1000 - 2,100mm	Full sun	Sandy, loam		1 - 2m per year, matures at 4 - 5 years
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	Coastal bush, coastal forests and on sand dunes, at various altitudes and latitudes	23 - 28°C but can tolerate 10 - 34°C	800 - 1,200mm but tolerates 600 - 1,800mm	Full sun or light shade	Various soils, pH 5 - 8	Frost	500 - 700mm per year, matures at 3 years
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	Dry woodland or savanna, especially on river banks, up to 1500m	10 - 35°C		Full sun, semi-shade	Various	Drought and frost-resistant	Fast growing, matures at 3 years
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		Dune bush and coastal forest, and inland in woodland and on forest margins	10 - 35°C		Light shade to full sun	Sandy loam, pH 4 - 7	Moderate drought tolerance	500 - 750mm per year, matures at 5 - 7 years
<i>Diospyros lycioides</i>	umbhongisa	Streams, rivers, forests, and thickets up to 1,000m	10 - 35°C		Full sun	Well-drained soil		Slow growing, matures at 4 years
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	Evergreen, montane, and scrub forest up to 2,400m	10 - 35°C		Sun or Shade	Loam		Slow growing
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	umqokolo	Dry areas, wooded grassland, on forest edges, up to 2,450m	10 - 35°C temperate to tropical	700 - 1,300mm	Full sun; semi-shade	Sandy loam, pH 5 - 7		600mm per year, matures at 4 - 5 years
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	Rainforest, riverine, ravine and coastal forests and in forests, up to 1,800m	Temperate		Shade, semi-shade	Well-drained soil in high water table	Frost	Slow growing, matures at 6 years
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	Wooded grassland; deciduous woodlands; bushland; coastal sand dunes; at elevations up to 1,950m	10 - 35°C		Full sun; semi-shade	Various	Frost	Fast growing
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umpayi, amakhiwane	Wet and dry forest and thickets, in riverine and ground-water forests in higher rainfall woodland and savanna, up to 2,200m	Tropical and sub-tropical		Full sun, semi-shade	Well-drained soil in high water table		Fast growing
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbu, amakhiwane	Riverbanks and in riverine forest, woodland and wooded grassland, up to 2,500m	10 - 35°C	800 - 1,800mm	Full sun, semi-shade	Well-drained soil in high water table	Frost	50cm per year
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	Scrub, open woodland and forest, up to 1,900m	15 - 25°C	800 - 1,800mm	Full sun, semi-shade	Various soils, pH 6.5	Cold conditions	Slow growing, matures at 2 years (grafted), 4 years (seedlings)

Species	Local name	Occurrence	Temperature	Rainfall	Light	Soil	Sensitivity	Growth rate
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	Arid karoo, coastal dune bush, evergreen montane forest and wooded grasslands			Semi-shade	Sandy, medium loamy, heavy clay		
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	Coastal and karroid scrub, deep evergreen forest, forest margins and ravines, rocky mountain slopes, near rivers and on stream banks	10 - 35°C		Full sun, semi-shade	Sandy, loam		Fast growing, matures at 2 years
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenya	Riverine forest; at elevations up to 1,400m	Tropical and sub-tropical		Full sun, semi-shade	Various soils, pH 6.5	Frost	1.5m per year
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		Savanna forest, on river-banks, grasslands, up to 1,500m	Tropical and sub-tropical		Full sun	Well-drained		
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	Open hillsides, in scrub bush; moist wooded kloofs and closed forests	Tropical and sub-tropical		Semi-shade		Frost-resistant	50cm per year, matures at 3 years
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	Near rivers, sandy banks, coastal dunes	Semi-arid; hot, dry areas	250 - 1,500mm	Full sun	Alluvial sands; sandy, clay, loam, pH 6.5		Slow growing
<i>Millettia grandis</i>	umsimbeeti	KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape. It is most common in Pondoland. Up to 600m altitudes		High	Full sun; shade	Sandy	Frost-resistant	80 - 100cm per year
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>		Rocky outcrops, wooded hillsides, riverine and forest fringes, open, dry woodland and bushveld	15 - 25°C	Low	Full sun; semi-shade	Various soils, pH 6.5	Frost	Fast growing, matures at 3 years
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	Riverbanks and swamps, occasionally in grasslands with high water table, Up to 3,000m	15 - 35°C	500 - 5,000mm	Full sun; light shade	Various, waterlogged or poor dry, pH 5 - 8		Matures at 5 years
<i>Portulacaria afra</i>	igqwaniitsha	Warm situations on rocky slopes in succulent karoo scrub, thicket, bushveld and dry river valleys	Temperate	Low	Full sun	Various	Frost-resistant	Fast growing
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga, ikhamanga	Coastal dune vegetation and in evergreen forests near the coast		High	Full sun	Various	Frost-resistant	Fast growing
<i>Syzigium cordatum</i>	injomi, umdoni	Near fresh water or along fresh watercourses, medium- to high-latitude forests, riverine thickets	10 - 35°C	600 - 1,500mm	Full sun; morning sun; semi-shade	Sandy, loam, pH 5 - 8		1m per year
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	Along riverbanks, forest margins, dry wooded valleys and hillsides in areas with little frost up to 1,800m	Warm	Low	Full sun	Well-drained		80cm per year, matures at 1 year
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	Riverine forest and bushveld up to 1,800m	19 - 31°C	600 - 2,300mm	Full sun, semi-shade	Clay, loam, pH 6.5		1.5m per year, matures at 6 years
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	Grassland, thicket and open woodlands, often on termite mounds, in rocky places and dunes, at elevations up to 1,500m	12 - 36°C	700 - 1,500mm	Full sun, semi-shade	Sandy, loam, pH 5 - 8	Drought and frost-resistant	50cm per year
<i>Ziziphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	Woodlands, open scrubland, on rocky koppies, open grasslands, along streams, valley bottoms and forest margins, up to 2,000m	12 - 30°C	440 - 1,200mm	Full sun	Various		30cm per year

Table A: Measurements of plants for long-term observation

A1: Dumasi Creche

Species	Name	Number at site N at planting	Root circumference (cm) C at planting	Root collar diameter (cm) RCD at planting	Height (cm) H at planting	N at 3 months	C (cm) at 3 months	RCD (cm) at 3 months	H (cm) at 3 months	N at 6 months	C (cm) at 6 months	RCD (cm) at 6 months	H (cm) at 6 months
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	7	2	0.64	22								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	4	6.5	2.07	71								
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	3	2.5	0.80	12								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	3	4.5	1.43	42								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	4	13	4.14	165								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	5	9	2.87	32								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	4	1.27	32								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	42	3	0.96	34								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	2	6	1.91	52								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umthumbe	2	3	0.96	26								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	4	8	2.55	70								
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	1	6	1.91	96								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	1	13	4.14	99								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	1	9	2.87	103								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	2	6	1.91	50								
<i>Ficus sur</i>	amakhiwane	1	5	1.59	66								
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	1	2.5	0.80	34								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>		3	3	0.96	40								
Total		90											

A2: Mtolani Community Garden and Nursery

Species	Name	Number at site N at planting	Root circumference (cm) C at planting	Root collar diameter (cm) RCD at planting	Height (cm) H at planting	N at 3 months	C (cm) at 3 months	RCD (cm) at 3 months	H (cm) at 3 months	N at 6 months	C (cm) at 6 months	RCD (cm) at 6 months	H (cm) at 6 months
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>		11	4	1.27	73								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>		8	3	0.96	32								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	7	6	1.91	40								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	11	4.5	1.43	52								
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	mqokolo	4	4	1.27	53								
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>	Red milkwood	8	3.5	1.11	41								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	16	2.5	0.80	37								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkukhlu	16	3	0.96	29								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	2	4	1.27	43								
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	6	2	0.64	24								
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu	8	1.5	0.48	21								
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	1	5	1.59	70								
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	2	3	0.96	72								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	16	2	0.64	25								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	7	8	2.55	43								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	2	3.5	1.11	78								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	2	3	0.96	52								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	4	4	1.27	42								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	6	7	2.23	42								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	2	12	3.82	156								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	1	6.5	2.07	97								
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	2	2	0.64	23								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umthumbe	1	7	2.23	70								
Total		143											

A3: Baleni School

Species	Name	Number at site N at planting	Root circumference (cm) C at planting	Root collar diameter (cm) RCD at planting	Height (cm) H at planting	N at 3 months	C (cm) at 3 months	RCD (cm) at 3 months	H (cm) at 3 months	N at 6 months	C (cm) at 6 months	RCD (cm) at 6 months	H (cm) at 6 months
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	28	5	1.59	61								
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		5	5	1.59	80								
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>		9	6	1.91	36								
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	1	5	1.59	85								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	3	14	4.46	242								
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>		9	4	1.27	75								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>		5	9	2.87	158								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>		2	4	1.27	48								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	6.5	2.07	40.5								
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbe	9	3	0.96	16								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>		5	2	0.64	30								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	mkuhlu	16	4	1.27	52								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	msinsi	1	5	1.59	60								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	1	4	1.27	100								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	18	1.5	0.48	16								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	11	3	0.96	39								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	4	3.5	1.11	25								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skemanga	5	11	3.50	26.5								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	2	5	1.59	29.5								
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadamkawu	3	1	0.32	14								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	amakhiwane	2	4	1.27	79								
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	mqokolo	2	3.5	1.11	35								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	1	6	1.91	28								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	4	4	1.27	58								
<i>Carissa edulis</i>		2	1	0.32	11								
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		6	1	0.32	20								
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	2	17	5.41	47								
Total		160											

A4: Xolobeni School

Species	Name	Number at site N at planting	Root circumference (cm) C at planting	Root collar diameter (cm) RCD at planting	Height (cm) H at planting	N at 3 months	C (cm) at 3 months	RCD (cm) at 3 months	H (cm) at 3 months	N at 6 months	C (cm) at 6 months	RCD (cm) at 6 months	H (cm) at 6 months
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	1	10	3.18	192								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	2	4	1.27	67								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	9	2.5	0.80	35								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	28	5	1.59	61								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	2	35	11.15	23								
<i>Portulacaria afra</i>	spekboom	3	4	1.27	10								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	4	13	4.14	38								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>		2	4.5	1.43	26								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	4	1.27	28								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	1	3.5	1.11	86								
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>		1	4	1.27	112								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	2	6	1.91	30								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	1	8	2.55	216								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	1	4	1.27	51								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	1	5	1.59	31								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	2	6.5	2.07	77								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	2	3	0.96	52								
Total		66											

PLANT PROPAGATION METHODS

Treated seeds

Seed Scarification

umtenatane
(*Diospyros whyteana*)

red milkwood
(*Mimusops zeyheri*)

Drying overnight

umqokolo
(*Dovyalis caffra*)

umpayi
(*Ficus natalensis*)

umthumbu
(*Ficus sur*)

Overnight soaking

umdubu (*Combretum erythrophyllum*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

umsimbeeti
(*Milletia grandis*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Warm water soaking

umgadankawu
(*Albizia adianthifolia*)

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umbhongisa
(*Diospyros lycoides*)

umpfafa
(*Ziziphus mucronata*)

Stored seeds

Stored seeds

umgadankawu
(*Albizia adianthifolia*)

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

ilala
(*Hyphaene coriacea*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

red milkwood
(*Mimusops zeyheri*)

Cuttings

Suckers

ilala
(*Hyphaene coriacea*)

isundu
(*Phoenix reclinata*)

skamanga
(*Strelitzia nicolai*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

Heeled cuttings treated with hormones

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umqokolo
(*Dovyalis caffra*)

umsinsi
(*Erythrina lysistemon*)

umpayi
(*Ficus natalensis*)

umthumbu
(*Ficus sur*)

amabimbi
(*Garcinia livingstonei*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

orange bird-berry
(*Hoslundia opposita*)

uthongothi
(*Hyperacanthus amoenus*)

igqwaniitsha
(*Portulacaria afra*)

iboza
(*Tetradenia riparia*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

Truncheons cut and shade dried

umsinsi
(*Erythrina lysistemon*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Air layering

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umthumbu/amakhiwane
(*Ficus sur*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Developing capacity for Indigenous Community Agroforestry in the Amadiba area of Eastern Mpondoland